

EVALUATING THE USE OF ELASTOMERS IN IMPROVING BLAST RESISTANCE OF FIBRE-METAL COMPOSITES

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Abstract

This paper investigates the effectiveness of different Fibre Metal Laminates (FML) when subjected to blast loading. The blast loading was applied using ANSYS in order to accurately model the impact. In total, three different laminates were investigated: a GLARE laminate, a GLARE laminate with a central FRP layer replaced with Duro 30 elastomer and a GLARE laminate with a central FRP layer replaced with Duro 70 elastomer. The stresses, displacements and energy absorption values were analysed for each of these when subjected to 5 different loading intensities. It was found from the analysis that the addition of an elastomer can help increase the blast performance of a laminate, but the addition of an elastomer does not guarantee this. However, the stiffness of the laminate with an elastomer layer is reduced in comparison to the stiffness of the GLARE laminate. So a compromise between the strength and stiffness must be attained for structural application of elastomer based FMLs.

1 Introduction

There has been an increasing interest in lightweight, blast resistant laminates for use in the aerospace industry. Blast resistant laminates have the potential to greatly increase the safety of aircraft. However, the main challenge is to reduce the cost and weight of the blast resistant laminates as they are currently too heavy and expensive to be feasible for usage in aerospace applications.

The primary laminates being investigated are fibre-metal laminates (FML). One example of this is the "Glass-Reinforced Fibre Metal Laminate" (GLARE) panels, which are used in part of the fuselage of the A-380. Analysis of GLARE panels has shown that they provide superior blast resistance compared to monolithic metal panels [1].

Other laminates have also been analysed, such as polyurea coated panels [2]. It was observed that a layer of polyurea sandwiched in between two layers of glass-epoxy was more effective than a standard "E-glass vinyl ester" (EVE) composite panel. The blast performance of the panel with an elastomer layer was enhanced by more than 100% in comparison to the standard EVE panel. However, a 60% increase in mass is the trade-off for this enhancement in resistance.

In this study, the effectiveness of FMLs containing an elastomer layer to withstand blast loads is studied. These laminates have the potential to offer increased blast resistance making them an attractive option for use in the aerospace industry.

2 Panel Configuration and Analysis Methodology

The panels analysed in the present study were square GLARE panels with 0.3 m edge length. The four edges of the panels were simply-supported, with the displacements constrained in all directions. These constraints were imposed to model a section of the wall of an aircraft. All the panels had a thickness of 2 mm (Figure 1).

The GLARE laminated panels consist of layers of both Aluminium and FRP (Figure 2). In this study, one of the FRP layers was replaced with an elastomer layer. The three laminates analysed are: (i) A base GLARE laminate made up of alternate Aluminium and FRP layers, (ii) Duro 30 laminate - a GLARE laminate with the central FRP layer replaced by a Duro 30 layer of the same thickness (0.125 mm), and (iii) Duro 70 laminate - a GLARE laminate with the central FRP layer replaced with a Duro 70 layer of equal thickness. The elastomer layer placement is as central as possible so It was decided that layer 9 (9th layer from the left Figure 2), an FRP layer, would be replaced firstly with the Duro 30 elastomer, then with the harder Duro 70

elastomer which is a more rigid than the Duro 30 elastomer.

The blast loading was simulated by applying an equivalent pressure on one of the faces of the panel. Five loading conditions were considered using applied pressures of 1, 10, 50, 100 and 1000 kPa. These pressure loads were applied to the central one-third of the panel (100 mm × 100 mm section) as indicated in Figure 1.

The element type used for the analysis of the FMLs was the 4-node layered SHELL181 element, which allows for material and geometric nonlinearities. It supports the hyper-elastic Mooney-Rivlin model [3] for the elastomeric materials used. The two coefficient Mooney-Rivlin model is used for both the Duro 30 and Duro 70 materials. The coefficients for these elastomers are presented in Table 1.

The commercial finite element program ANSYS was used for the stress analyses under blast loading. Each laminate was analysed using a nonlinear dynamic transient analysis. The load was ramped up from zero, reaching the maximum pressure load at 2 milliseconds. This was then ramped back down to zero over 23 milliseconds. The responses of each panel, including stress, displacement and energy, were then analysed after the load was applied.

3 Results

3.1 Displacement variation

It was evident in analysing the laminates, that the laminates with an elastomer layer as opposed to the FRP layer in the GLARE laminate have greater total displacements under blast loading. This is due to the reduced stiffness of the laminates with the elastomer layer. The Duro 30 laminate has a maximum displacement of 3.5 mm in the centre of the panel under a blast load of 50 kPa. The more rigid Duro 70 laminate has a maximum displacement of 3.4 mm under the same load. In comparison to the standard GLARE laminate, these laminates have high displacements. The GLARE laminate with the FRP layer has a maximum displacement of 3.1 mm in the centre of the panel. Both the Duro 30 and Duro 70 elastomers have much lower stiffness's in comparison to the FRP.

It can be observed from the displacement plots for both the laminate with a Duro 30 layer and the laminate with a Duro 70 layer that the displacement patterns are similar. This is due to the elastomeric

properties of the Duro 30 and Duro 70. The laminate with a Duro 30 layer has a slightly higher maximum displacement. This backs up the strain energy density results, as the laminate with the Duro 30 layer has higher elastic strain energy in comparison to the laminate with the Duro 70 layer. This shows that the laminate with a Duro 30 layer is more effective at absorbing energy than the laminate with a Duro 70 layer. The Duro 30 laminate is more effective at absorbing the blast at lower blast pressure loads. As the blast load is increased to a maximum pressure of 1 MPa, and the in-plane stiffnesses become more dominant, the displacements of the GLARE laminate, the Duro 30 laminate and the Duro 70 laminate are all within 0.2 mm of each other.

The larger displacements in the Duro 30 and Duro 70 laminates also mean that the laminates are closer to failure. The layers of the laminate are being displaced by a larger amount thus the strain is larger leading to larger stress. This could lead to problems as the fibres or Aluminium may fail making the structure significantly weaker.

3.2 Stress variation

The von Mises stress produced in the GLARE laminate from the blast load is the lowest in comparison to the GLARE laminates with elastomer layers. The maximum von Mises stress for the laminate with a Duro 70 layer is higher than the maximum von Mises stress for the laminate with a Duro 30 layer. This is due to the much higher rigidity of the harder Duro 70 elastomer. The contour plots for both the laminate with the Duro 30 layer and the laminate with the Duro 70 layer are very similar. This is due to the layup of the panels; the panels are both asymmetric with the 9th layer being replaced with an elastomer. Relative to the overall panel stiffness, the effect of varying the elastomer hardness is insignificant. The transient principal stresses for all three laminates for the central 9th layer are shown in Figure 4. It can be observed from these plots that the Duro 30 and Duro 70 laminates behave in a similar manner, this is due to the similar properties of the Duro 30 and Duro 70 elastomers.

It can also be noticed from the results of all the laminates that the stress does not increase in a linear

fashion with the applied load. This is due to the stress stiffening occurring in the panels.

It can be noticed from the failure criteria of the Tsai-Wu index and the maximum stress index that neither the Duro 30 nor Duro 70 laminates fails under the given loading conditions. The maximum stress index for the Duro 30 and Duro 70 laminates is 0.551 and 0.654 respectively. This is lower than that for the GLARE panel under the same loading conditions of 0.73. This shows that the Duro 30 laminate is the furthest from failure with the GLARE laminate being closest at 0.51. The Tsai-Wu index shows a similar trend with the Duro 30 and Duro 70 indices being 0.301 and 0.426 respectively.

3.3 Energy variation

The strain energy absorbed by the panel, which indicates the shock absorbing property, of the laminate was monitored as observed in Figure 5. The maximum strain energy densities were 19,100, 21,500, and 5,890 J/m³ for the FRP, Duro 30 and Duro 70 laminates, respectively. The Duro 30 laminate has a peak strain energy density of 21,500 J/m³, which is more than 2000 J/m³ more than that of the FRP laminate. This is expected as the Duro 30 elastomer is softer and less rigid than FRP, and hence it has a greater energy absorption capacity.

However, the strain energy density for the Duro 70 laminate was found to be considerably lower than that of the FRP laminate. So the Duro 70 elastomer is less effective at absorbing energy from the blast in comparison to the standard FRP based GLARE panel. This is because of the higher hardness of the Duro 70 elastomer.

The maximum strain energy density of the Duro 70 laminate is also approximately 3.5 times lower than that of the Duro 30 laminate. Hence, the Duro 30 laminate is significantly more effective to withstand the blast loading compared to the Duro 70 laminate. This is because Duro 30 elastomer is considerably softer and more compliant, thus it can absorb more energy imparted by the blast loading.

4 Convergence Study

A study of convergence was carried out in order to ensure that the mesh being used was satisfactory. The final mesh used in the analysis was a 30 element by 30 element mesh, with a total of 900 elements. This provided greater accuracy over a 15 by 15

element mesh as the 15 by 15 mesh provided larger discrepancies in the maximum displacement values. The criteria used in order to determine convergence of the results was the percentage difference of the maximum displacements to be less than 1%. It was found from the convergence study between the 30 by 30 element mesh and the 60 by 60 element mesh that the results do converge, this can be seen below in Table 2. This shows that the 30 by 30 element mesh is suitable for use in this study.

Load Cases:

A – 1 kPa B – 10 kPa C – 50 kPa D – 100 kPa
E – 1 MPa

Laminates:

- 1 – GLARE laminate with alternating FRP and Aluminium layers
- 2 – GLARE laminate with a central FRP layer replaced with a Duro 30 layer
- 3 – GLARE laminate with a central FRP layer replaced with a Duro 70 layer

5 Validation

5.1 Analytical

In order to determine whether the solutions obtained for the analysis using the GLARE plate are accurate, a comparison was conducted. The comparison was between the equation for the natural frequency and the natural frequency obtained from ANSYS.

The equation below [3] was used in order to calculate the natural frequency (ω_{mn}) of the GLARE laminate.

$$\omega_{mn}^2 = \frac{\pi^4}{\rho h b^4} [D_{11} m^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) m^2 n^2 + D_{22} n^4] \quad (Eq.1)$$

where the values: $D_{11} = 44.79$ Nm, $D_{12} = 13.05$ Nm, $D_{22} = 43.6$ Nm and $D_{66} = 13.33$ Nm. The average mass density is $\rho = 2340$ Kg/m³.

This resulted in a fundamental natural frequency of $f = 104.51$ Hz, which is almost identical to the ANSYS result of 104.88 Hz

5.2 Numerical

A validation study was carried out in order to compare the numerical model used and a real life situation. For this analysis the EVE composite used in Tekalur's study [2] was used. This was chosen due to the availability of the material properties and blast pressure data.

5.2.1 Modelling Approach

A 0.45 MPa blast on a 102 mm by 229 mm panel was analysed, in which the blast was concentrated in the centre of the panel. The blast was modelled as a 75 mm by 75 mm square in the centre of the panel. The analysis conducted was a nonlinear transient analysis, similar to that used in the rest of this study. A rise and decay time of 0.1 milliseconds was used in the analysis.

5.2.2 Results

The analysis produced a maximum displacement in the centre of the panel, similar to that of the experimental situation. This can be observed in [2]. The maximum displacement for this panel is 12.2 mm. This is smaller than the experimental value of 14 mm. The numerical value is 87% of the experimental value. When the mesh was further refined, there a negligible change in the numerical result, therefore the numerical solution obtained has converged.

The difference between the two values could be due to the rise and decay times used in the analysis. A rise time of 0.1 ms was used as it is shown in the experimental study that this is the approximate rise time of the actual blast. However, this is an approximate value so is not completely accurate, accounting for some discrepancy in the experimental and numerical solutions. There could also be imperfections in the materials used which are not accounted for in the analysis, for example, the volume fraction could be lower than expected thus affecting the mechanical properties of the EVE material. The structural damping of the panel was not taken into account as well; this could cause some differences in displacements.

6 Application of blast load modelling

The GLARE-elastomer FML has proven to be very promising for applications involving blast loading. This could be used in order to help increase the blast resistance of planes as it provides a relatively lightweight, blast resistant laminate. This is an improvement over the GLARE panels which have been designed for this purpose. However, the laminate may need some form of stiffening as the elastomer reduces the overall stiffness of the GLARE panels. A Fibre Reinforced Elastomer could be used as opposed to the elastomer as this would

provide a similar stiffness as the FRP in the GLARE panel while maintaining the added blast resistance from the elastomer. This blast resistant laminate is not only suitable for use in the aerospace industry; it could also be applied to military uses and to uses in the automotive industry.

7 Conclusions

The present study evaluated the effectiveness of the use of elastomer layers in fibre-metal laminates to provide improved blast resistance. It has been shown that the inclusion of an appropriate elastomer layer, such as a Duro 30 layer, as a replacement of the FRP layer increases the energy absorption capacity from the blast. Although the overall stiffness of the GLARE panels is decreased upon adding the elastomer layer, the blast resistance is greatly improved. It was also shown that the addition of any elastomer layer does not necessarily enhance the blast resistance compared to the conventional FRP based FMLs. For example, the Duro 70 elastomer is not suitable for use in enhancing the blast performance of FML. In contrary, it significantly degrades the blast resistance of the laminate in comparison to the FRP panel. This shows that the property of an elastomer used in a FML should be carefully chosen so as to improve the blast resistance of the resultant structural component.

Fig. 1. Blast load configuration (in mm)

Fig. 2. Schematic of the GLARE panel showing the standard (FRP), Duro 30 and Duro 70 laminate layups (the central green layer is elastomer for Duro 30 and Duro 70 laminates)

Fig. 3. A representative Duro 30 laminate displacement plot

Fig. 4a. – Principal stress variation with time for the GLARE laminate

Fig. 4b. – Principal stress variation with time for the Duro 30 laminate

Fig. 4c. – Principal stress variation with time for the Duro 70 laminate

Fig. 5a. - Strain energy density variation with time for the GLARE laminate

Fig. 5b. - Strain energy density variation with time for the Duro 30 laminate

Fig. 5c. - Strain energy density variation with time for the Duro 70 laminate

Load Case					
Laminate	A	B	C	D	E
1	0	0.07	0.05	0.02	0.08
2	0.33	0.24	0.28	0.19	0.33
3	0.56	0.13	0.15	0.31	0.22

References

- [1] Langdon, G.S., et al., *Response of GLARE panels to blast loading*. 2009.
- [2] Tekalur, S.A., A. Shukla, and K. Shivakumar, *Blast resistance of polyurea based layered composite materials*. 2007.
- [3] Jones, R.M., *Mechanics of Composite Materials*. 1975, Hemisphere Publishing Corporation: New York, NY, USA.

Table 1 – Material Properties

Material	E (GPa)	σ_{max} (MPa)	τ_{max} (MPa)	ν	ρ (kg/m ³)
Aluminium	72	485	280	0.33	1980
FRP	E_x : 52.36 E_y : 15.06 E_z : 15.06	σ_x : 2550 σ_y : 103 σ_z : 103	90	ν_{xy} : 0.26 ν_{yz} : 0.33 ν_{xz} : 0.26	2700
Duro 30	C_1 : 124100	C_2 : 31000		0.49	1000
Duro 70	C_1 : 477200	C_2 : 119300		0.49	1000

Table 2: Percentage difference in maximum displacement between 30 x 30 mesh and 60 x 60 mesh